

Validation of Polars DataFrame and LazyFrame

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Validation of Polars DataFrame and LazyFrame

1.1 Author

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1.2 Description

This work item significantly expands Snakemake's data validation capabilities. Specifically, it adds support for validating both `polars DataFrame` and `LazyFrame` objects in addition to the existing `YAML` and `pandas DataFrame` support. This allows users to ensure the integrity and correctness of their input data more effectively. Specifically:

1.2.1 Summary of Enhancements

With this work item, `polars DataFrame` and `LazyFrame` objects can also be validated just like a `pandas DataFrame`.

1.2.2 Impact

These improvements enhance the versatility and usability of Snakemake for data science workflows, since the addition of Polars support enables users to leverage the performance benefits of this library while maintaining data integrity.

1.3 Associated Project Workitem

- [PR 3262 - feat: add support for validation of polars dataframe and lazyframe](#)

1.4 Acknowledgement

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